

MODERN DIRECTIONS OF LINGUISTICS AND THEIR ANALYSIS AND PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT This article reviews the modern directions of linguistics and considers their relevance today.

Keywords: linguistics - linguistics, terminology, sociolinguistics, static linguistics, computational linguistics

INTRODUCTION

The term linguistics is actively used in a number of European countries: English, French, German, Spanish, Russian and other languages, and means the science of language. The root of this word is lingua, which means language. Therefore, the Uzbek alternative and synonym of the term linguistics is linguistics, and they enter into a mutually synonymous relationship.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The science of linguistics or linguistics studies and analyzes the tool of communication, which is a unique complex social phenomenon - language as a system - as a whole object. In the same process, it is observed in various forms. This comes from the nature of the language, which has a social character, from the need to study and examine it from different angles, and it is absolutely correct from the point of view of science.

Linguistics is manifested in the following forms in the process of learning a language, which is an extremely powerful symbol of spirituality, the wealth of the nation:

1. Dynamic linguistics.
2. Static linguistics.

3. Synchronous linguistics.
4. Diachronic linguistics.
5. Intralinguistics.
6. Extralinguistics.
7. Paralinguistics.
8. Psycholinguistics.
9. Sociolinguistics.
10. Mathematical linguistics.
12. Cognitive linguistics.
13. Pragmalinguistics.
14. Linguistic culture.

DISCUSSION

1. Dynamic linguistics. Dynamic linguistics mainly studies the language in its real existence, in the active performance of various tasks in the communicative process, in "development", in change.
2. Static linguistics. Static linguistics distinguishes and describes a specific period (section) in language activity that is completely synchronized. This field of linguistics, unlike dynamic linguistics, is completely removed from the process of development and change in the language, without approaching it, it investigates the state of a certain "stiff" part of the language related to the present - modern era.
3. Synchronous linguistics. Synchronous linguistics is inextricably linked with static and structural linguistics and serves to describe the "stagnant" and "stagnant" state of the language in a certain period.
4. Diachronic linguistics. Diachronic linguistics is inextricably linked with dynamic and atomistic linguistics, and studies the development of language and the laws and results of the development of language units.
5. Intralinguistics (internal linguistics). Internal linguistics studies the system connection and relationship of language units without dependence on extralinguistic

factors. The research source of internal linguistics is phonology, lexicology and grammar.

6. Extralinguistics (external linguistics). External linguistics studies the development and function of language in relation to socio-political, socio-historical, ethnic, geographical factors. Accordingly, this linguistics examines language as a social phenomenon.

7. Paralinguistics. Paralinguistics is directly related to speech activity, and includes hand and face movements (gesture, facial expressions), speech pitch, expressive- is a field that studies a number of aspects such as emotional coloring.

8. Psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics, as a generalization (synthesis) of the sciences of psychology and linguistics, studies the speech process from the point of view of content, communicative significance, orientation of the act of speech to a certain socio-practical goal, and its conformity. He pays special attention to the unity of form and content in speech - expression of thought.

Psycholinguistics refers to the formation and reception of speech units based on linguistic capabilities, to mental states in the speech process (thought exchange-expression and understanding), including situation (situation), similarity (analogy), differentiation (differentiation), affectiveness, word pays special attention to the issues of the listener's and listener's mental state.

9. Sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics is formed from the necessary and logical connection of the sciences of sociology and linguistics and deals with the issue of the relationship between society and language (language and society). He interprets language as a social phenomenon. In this regard, the most important, main problem of sociolinguistics is to investigate the language - the nature of language as a social phenomenon, to determine its place and importance in society, in the science of linguistics.

Sociolinguistics mainly studies the connection between language and social relations, social life, development events, facts, and the reasons for this connection.

In fact, this field analyzes the events, processes, and changes resulting from the influence of external-extralinguistic factors (factors) in the life and development of society. So, sociolinguistics studies how social factors affect the language, how they are manifested in the language system (structure), and in what form they are reflected.

We remind you that sociolinguistics expands its activity with the methodology of statistical data, population census and questionnaire data¹.

10. Mathematical linguistics. Mathematical linguistics examines the possibilities of using mathematical methods (for example, statistical methods, information theory, etc.) in the process of language learning and description.

11. Computer linguistics. Computational linguistics is a branch of applied linguistics, the main goal of which is to solve linguistic problems with the help of a computer, directly under its "leadership". More precisely, computer linguistics actively serves in a number of processes, such as teaching (learning) languages, evaluating knowledge of a specific subject, editing texts, translating from one language to another, conducting statistical research.

12. Cognitive linguistics. Cognitive linguistics is one of the newest areas in linguistics. This linguistics emerged from the necessary connection between the sciences of cognitology (a science that studies human knowledge) and linguistics, in order to work together.

13. Pragmalinguistics. Pragmatic linguistics is the result of cognitive (empirical) research and research at a new stage based on the achievements and results of structural linguistics. It takes the situation of use of the linguistic unit, speech activity as a system. Accordingly, a specific unit is studied and examined in cooperation with various non-linguistic factors and different levels in speech activity, realization, and manifestation in speech.

14. Linguistic culture. Lingvoculturalology was formed on the basis of the fields of linguistics, cultural studies, ethnography, psycholinguistics. He studies the

interaction and influence of culture, ethnos, national mentality based on the principles of the anthropocentric paradigm.

THE RESULT

So, the science of linguistics as a generality, as mentioned, researches the language system with all its essence, complexity, and unlimited communicative possibilities through its various features and fields. In the same process, he interacts and works in cooperation with a number of disciplines, and actively participates in the coverage of extremely urgent and extremely complex issues such as language and society, language and history, language and development, language and thinking, language and speech. .

CONCLUSION

The science of linguistics serves to confirm and prove that language is one of the most important, basic, and incomparable criteria for the development and prosperity of society. Also, it helps the learner to develop creative thinking by conveying to the learner the possibilities of the native language - the ways of expressing the same idea, thing and phenomenon in hundreds of ways, the uniqueness of thinking and the construction of the native language, which is fundamentally different from other languages, It serves as a solid foundation for the formation of national consciousness, national worldview, national pride and ideology by inculcating reflection of the world "in its own way".

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